

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 2

Бош муҳаррир:

Ризаев Жасур Алимжанович
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети ректори
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети Илмий ишлар ва инновациялар бўйича
проректори, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-3933

Масъул котиб:

Самиева Гулноза Утқуровна
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Нашр учун масъул:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети,
онкология кафедраси
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

ТАХРИРИЯТ КЕНГАШИ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

*Иммунология ва инсон геномикаси институти директори –
тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Ўзбекистон
Республикаси Фанлар академияси академиги*

Jin Young Choi

*Сеул миллий университети Стоматология мактаби оғиз ва
юз-жағ жарроҳлиги департаменти профессори, Жанубий
Кореянинг юз-жағ ва эстетик жарроҳлик ассоциацияси
президенти*

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаатовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор, Самарқанд
давлат тиббиёт университети проректори, 1-клиникаси бош
врачи. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Худоярова Дилдора Рахимовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети №1-сон Акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255*

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, доцент, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети Гистология, цитология ва
эмбриология кафедраси мудири
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

*тиббиёт фандар доктори, Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт
университети болалар жарроҳлиги кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент тиббиёт
академияси Оилавий тиббиётда акушерлик ва гинекология
кафедраси профессори **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Акбаров Миршавкат Мирлоимович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, В.Ваҳидов номидаги
Республика ихтисослаштирилган жарроҳлик маркази*

Саидов Садамир Аброрович

*тиббиёт фанлар доктори,
Тошкент фармацевтика институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Бабалжанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Тошкент педиатрия
тиббиёт институти, Тери-таносил, болалар
тери-таносил касалликлари ва ОИТС
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди, доцент, Тошкент
педиатрия тиббиёт институти Факультет болалар
хирургия кафедраси. **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-5409-4327*

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

*тиббиёт фанлари номзоди,
Самарқанд давлат тиббиёт университети
№2-сон Педиатрия, неонатология ва болалар
касаликлари пропедевтикаси кафедраси доценти.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергандовна

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, профессор
Тошкент давлат стоматология институти
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

*тиббиёт фанлари доктори, Самарқанд давлат
тиббиёт университети, онкология кафедраси доценти
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналлов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Главный редактор:

Ризаев Жасур Алимджанович
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, Ректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0001-5468-9403

Заместитель главного редактора:

Зиядуллаев Шухрат Худайбердиевич
доктор медицинских наук, проректор по научной
работе и инновациям Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-9309-

Ответственный секретарь:

Самиева Гульноза Уткуровна
доктор медицинских наук, доцент Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Ответственный за публикацию:

Шаханова Шахноза Шавкатовна
PhD кафедры онкологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ КОЛЛЕГИЯ:

Арипова Тамара Уктамовна

директор Института иммунологии и геномики человека
доктор медицинских наук, профессор, академик АН РУз

Jin Young Choi

профессор департамента оральной и челюстно-лицевой
хирургии школы стоматологии Стоматологического
госпиталя Сеульского национального университета,
Президент Корейского общества челюстно-лицевой и
эстетической хирургии

Абдуллаева Наргиза Нурмаатовна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор, проректор
Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248

Худоярова Дилдора Рахимовна

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой
Акушерства и гинекологии №1 Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255

Орипов Фирдавс Суръатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент, заведующий кафедрой
Гистологии, цитологии и эмбриологии Самаркандского
государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144

Мавлянов Фарход Шавкатович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Детской
хирургии Самаркандского государственного медицинского
университета, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0003-2650-4445

Магзумова Наргиза Махкамовна

Доктор медицинских наук, профессор кафедры
акушерства и гинекологии Семейной медицины
Ташкентской медицинской академии
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918

Акбаров Миршавкат Миролимович

доктор медицинских наук,
Республиканский специализированный центр
хирургии имени академика В.Вахидова

Саидов Саидмир Аброрович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский
фармацевтический институт
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428

Бабаджанов Ойбек Абдужаббарович

доктор медицинских наук, Ташкентский педиатрический
медицинский институт, кафедра Дерматовенерология, детская
дерматовенерология и СПИД, **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-3022-916X

Теребаев Билим Алдамуратович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Факультетской
детской хирургии Ташкентского педиатрического
медицинского института.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327

Юлдашев Ботир Ахматович

кандидат медицинских наук, доцент кафедры Педиатрии,
неонатологии и протекции детских болезней №2
Самаркандского государственного медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523

Ибрагимова Малика Худайбергеновна

доктор медицинских наук, профессор
Ташкентского государственного
стоматологического института
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742

Рахимов Нодир Махамматкулович

доктор медицинских наук, доцент кафедры
онкологии Самаркандского государственного
медицинского университета
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503

Верстка: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Chief Editor:

Rizaev Jasur Alimjanovich
MD, DSc, Professor of Dental Medicine,
Rector of the Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5468-9403

Deputy Chief Editor:

Ziyadullaev Shukhrat Khudayberdievich
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Vice-Rector for scientific work
and Innovation, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9309-3933

Responsible secretary:

Samieva Gulnoza Utkurovna
doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6142-7054

Responsible for publication:

Shakhanova Shakhnoza Shaykatovna
PhD Department of Oncology
Samarkand State medical university
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-0888-9150

EDITORIAL BOARD:

Aripova Tamara Uktamovna

*Director of the Institute of Immunology and Human Genomics -
Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Academician of the
Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan*

Jin Young Choi

*Professor Department of Oral and Maxillofacial
Surgery School of Dentistry Dental Hospital
Seoul National University, President of the
Korean Society of Maxillofacial Aesthetic Surgery*

Abdullaeva Nargiza Nurmatovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Vice-Rector
Samarkand State Medical University, Chief Physician of
the 1st Clinic **ORCID ID:** 0000-0002-7529-4248*

Khudoyarova Dildora Rakhimovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology,
Samarkand State Medical University No.1
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5770-2255*

Oripov Firdavs Suratovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Head of the Department of Histology, Cytology and
Embryology of Samarkand State Medical University.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-0615-0144*

Mavlyanov Farkhod Shavkatovich

*Doctor of Medicine, Associate Professor of Pediatric
Surgery, Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2650-4445*

Magzumova Nargiza Makhamovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor, Department
of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Family Medicine,
Tashkent Medical Academy
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9313-4918*

Akbarov Mirshavkat Mirolimovich

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Republican Specialized Center of Surgery
named after academician V.Vakhidov*

Saidov Saidamir

*Doctor of Medical Sciences,
Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute,
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-6616-5428*

Babadjanov Oybek Abdujabbarovich

*Doctor of sciences in medicine, Tashkent Pediatric
Medical Institute, Department of Dermatovenerology,
pediatric dermatovenerology and AIDS
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3022-916X*

Terebaev Bilim Aldamuratovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor,
Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute,
Faculty of Children Department of Surgery.
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-5409-4327.*

Yuldashev Botir Akhmatovich

*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of
Pediatrics, Neonatology and Propaedeutics of Pediatrics,
Samarkand State Medical University No. 2.
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-2442-1523*

Ibragimova Malika Xudayberganovna

*Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor,
Tashkent State Dental Institute
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-9235-1742*

Rahimov Nodir Maxamatkulovich

*DSc, Associate Professor of Oncology,
Samarkand State Medical University
ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5272-5503*

Page Maker: Khurshid Mirzakhmedov

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

1. **Urinbaeva A. Nilufar, Abduganieva F. Dilsuz**
THE PROBLEM OF FETAL GROWTH RETRACTION SYNDROME IN OBSTETRICS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....10

THERAPY

2. **Jakbarova A. Mohida Juraeva A. Mohigul**
CLINICAL AND EPIDEMIOLOGICAL CLASSIFICATION OF COMMUNITY-ACQUIRED PNEUMONIA.....22
3. **Boltaev J. Kamol, Rizaeva J. Malika**
THE ROLE OF PREDICTORS IN THE FORMATION OF THROMBOSIS IN ATRIAL FIBRILLATION (REVIEW ARTICLE).....27
4. **Akhmedov A. Ibrat, Uralov Sh Rustam, Akhmedova A. Gulchekhra**
THE ROLE OF ANTIFILAGGRIN ANTIBODIES IN THE DIAGNOSIS AND PROGNOSIS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS AT AN EARLY STAGE.....33
5. **Akhmedova Sh. Nilufar, Rizayeva J. Malika**
CHANGES IN ANTITHROMBIN INDICATORS IN ATRIAL FIBRILLATION.....39
6. **Agababyan R. Irina, Djabbarova M. Nafisa**
CURRENT ISSUES IN MODERN TREATMENT OF NON-ALCOHOLIC FATTY LIVER DISEASE.....44
7. **Abdushukurova R. Komila, Akhmedov A. Ibrat**
FOUNDATIONS OF IMMUNOPATHOGENESIS OF RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS: REVIEW OF LITERATURE.....55
8. **Makhatmuradova N.Nargiza**
FEATURES OF HIGH-RESOLUTION COMPUTED TOMOGRAPHY IN NONSPECIFIC INTERSTITIAL PNEUMONIA.....66
9. **Akhmedov A. Ibrat, Uralov Sh Rustam, Eshmuratov E. Sardor**
FEATURES OF THE SUBPOPULATION COMPOSITION OF PERIPHERAL BLOOD LYMPHOCYTES IN THE FIRST PERIODS OF THE DISEASE IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS.....73
10. **Kityan S.Aleksandr**
COMPREHENSIVE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE CURRENT EPIDEMIOLOGICAL SITUATION REGARDING THE INCIDENCE AND PREVALENCE OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE(LITERARY REVIEW).....78

SURGERY

11. **Mamanov Ch Muxammad., Arziev A Ismoil, Arzieva B Gulnora**
DIFFERENTIATED SURGICAL TACTICS FOR COMPLICATED FORMS OF LIVER ECHINOCOCCOSIS.....83
12. **Zohidova H Sanoat, Mamataliyev R. Abdumalik**
DESPITE THE COMPLEXITY AND SERIOUSNESS OF THE DISEASE, MODERN TREATMENT METHODS CAN ACHIEVE POSITIVE RESULTS AND IMPROVE THE PROGNOSIS OF PATIENTS WITH DESTRUCTIVE PANCREATITIS.....91
13. **Achilov T. Mirzakarim, Ahmedov K. Gayrat, Mirmuxammedov Dj.Nasimjon, Shakulov M. Azizbek**
INTRAGENATION OF PROLOSED RECTUM (CASE FROM PRACTICE).....97

14. **Babajanov S. Akhmadjon, Akhmedov I. Adkham, Shamsiev J. Shokhzod**
IMPROVEMENT OF THE INTRAOPERATIVE THYROMETRY METHOD IN THE SURGICAL TREATMENT OF BENIGN THYROID GLAND PATHOLOGIES.....104
15. **Khursanov E. Yokub, Makhmudov B. Saydinjon, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar**
USE OF TENSION-FREE HERNIOPLASTY IN SURGICAL TREATMENT OF STARGED ANTERIOR HERNIA ABDOMINAL WALL (LITERATURE REVIEW).....113
16. **Avazov A. Abdurakhim., Shakirov M. Bobur., Hakimov A. Erkin**
TREATMENT OF ISOLATED BURNS OF THE HAND AND FOOT IN A HUMID ENVIRONMENT WITH SILVER-CONTAINING PREPARATIONS.....120

DENTISTRY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

17. **Fozilov A. Uktam**
DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF THE DIAGNOSIS OF DENTAL ANOMALIES AND DEFORMATIONS USING A COMPUTER PROGRAM.....126
18. **Nurova N. Shoxsanam**
THE INCIDENCE OF CHRONIC DISSEMINATED PERIODONTITIS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF OSTEOPOROSIS IN WOMEN OF FERTILE AGE WITH BREAST CANCER.....136
19. **Ibragimova Kh. Malika, Ruzikulova Sh. Munira**
PERIODONTAL STATUS ACCORDING TO THE CPITN INDEX IN PATIENTS WITH FATTY HEPATOSIS.....141
20. **Kamalova R. Feruza, Rakhimov Kh. Jahongir.**
INFLUENCE OF MAGNETOTHERAPY ON VARIOUS SYSTEMS OF THE BODY AND ON THE PROCESS OF WOUND HEALING IN CHILDREN WITH CLEFT LIP.....149
21. **Gaffarov A. Sunnatullo, Astanov M. Otabek**
DENTAL CONDITION OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES IN PATIENTS WITH PSYCHIATRIC PATHOLOGIES.....154
22. **Kamalova R. Feruza, Mamedova Sh. Nigina**
EVALUATION OF COMPLEX TREATMENT OF ODONTOGENIC PURULENT INFLAMMATORY DISEASES OF THE JAWS.....161
23. **Agababyan R. Irina, Ismoilov M. Rajabboy**
SYSTEMIC INFLAMMATION IN ATHEROSCLEROSIS ON THE BACKGROUND OF CHRONIC PERIODONTITIS.....166
24. **Boymuradov A. Shukhrat, Ruzibayev R. Dilshod**
RESULTS OF ELIMINATING OF PERFORATION OF THE MAXILLARY SINUS BOTTOM USING PRF.....173
25. **Abasniya R. Surayyo**
LABORATORY INDICATORS OF IMPROVING METHODS OF TREATING PERIODONTITIS AMONG THE POPULATION OF KHOREZM REGION.....182
26. **Eronov Q. Yoqub**
THE INFLUENCE OF PATHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN THE MICROBIOCENOSIS OF PERIODONTAL TISSUES ON ORAL HYGIENE IN CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES.....187

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

27. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Nabiyev R. Ozod, Raupova M. Kamola, Boltayev I. Anvar**
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ACOUSTIC REFLEX OF THE INTRA-EAR MUSCLES IN OCCUPATIONAL HEARING DISORDERS.....193

28. **Xatamov A. Jakhongir, Amonov E. Ergashevich**
MODERN APPROACHES TO THE TREATMENT OF COMPLICATED FORMS OF
CHRONIC INFLAMMATION OF THE MIDDLE EAR.....200
29. **Lutfullayev U. Gairat, Ne`matov S. O`ktam, Khamraev Kh. Farid**
LOBULAR CAPILLARY HAEMANGIOMA OF THE NASAL CAVITY DURING
PREGNANCY: A CLINICAL CASE.....209
30. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Xayitov A. Alisher, Nabiyev R. Ozod, Dustboboyev S. Dilshod**
IMPROVEMENT OF THE SURGICAL APPROACH FOR CYSTIC LESIONS OF THE
MAXILLARY SINUS.....214

PEDIATRICS

31. **Rakhmatullaev A. Akmal, Terebaev A. Bilim, Mazhidov Kh. Temur**
MODERN VIEWS OF DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT PAYRE'S SYNDROME IN
CHILDREN.....221
32. **Garifulina M. Lilya M., Goyibova S. Nargiza**
MICROALBUMINURIA AS AN INDICATOR OF METABOLIC DISORDERS IN
OBESITY CHILDREN.....227
33. **Yusupova U. Umida**
PECULIARITIES OF CYTOKINE STATUS IN EARLY CHILDREN WITH NON-SOCIAL
PNEUMONIA LIVING IN ECOLOGICAL REGIONS.....233
34. **Kuryazova M. Sharofat, Khudaynazarova R. Salomat**
FREQUENCY AND STRUCTURE OF BRONCHOPULMONARY PATHOLOGY IN
CHILDREN OF DIFFERENT AGE GROUPS.....241

CHILDREN SURGERY

35. **Yuldashev A. Botir, Murodova D. Malika**
ASSESSMENT OF CARDIORENAL SYNDROME IN CHILDREN WITH ACUTE
NEPHRITIC SYNDROME.....247

PSYCHONEUROLOGY

36. **Rizaev A. Jasur, Khakimova Z. Sohuba**
BRAIN REGENERATION: STEM CELL THERAPY FOR NEURODEGENERATIVE
DISEASES.....255
37. **Kodirov A. Umid, Abdurakhimov Mukhiddin**
RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH
LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHY IN CHRONIC BRUCELLIOSIS.....262
38. **Kodirov A. Umid, Turdiev Dilmurod**
RESULTS OF CLINICAL AND NEUROLOGICAL INDICATIONS IN PATIENTS WITH
LUMBAR SPINE DORSOPATHY IN CASE OF HERPETIC INFECTION.....269
39. **Turaev M. Tolib, Kuchimova A. Charos**
CLINICAL SIGNIFICANS OF ANXIETY AND DEPRESSIVE DISORDERS IN PATIENTS
WITH METABOLIC SYNDROME.....275
40. **Muminov A. Bekzod, Matmurodov J. Rustambek, Khalimova M. Khanifa, Nazarova F. Madinabonu, Umirova M. Surayyo.**
CHANGED LEVELS OF INTERLEUKIN-6 IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE PATIENTS
WITH COVID-19.....281
41. **Mirjuraev M. Elbek, Samiev S. Asliddin, Urakov U. Shokir**
ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH
COGNITIVE CHANGES IN CHRONIC CEREBRAL CIRCULATION DISEASES.....289

ONCOLOGY AND GEMATOLOGY

42. **Ismailova A. Jadida, Yusupbekov A. Abrorjon, Tuychiyev D. Otabek**
STUDY OF HISTOPATHOLOGICAL STAGES OF THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE IN THE
EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF GASTRIC CANCER.....296
43. **Abdiyev Kattabek Makhmatovich**
COMPLICATIONS OF PRIMARY MYELOFIBROSIS AND TACTICS OF THEIR
TREATMENT.....303
44. **Azimova A. Makhbuba, Nasirova K. Khurshedakhon**
THYROID DYSFUNCTION IN BREAST CANCER.....316

REHABILITATION AND SPORTS MEDICINE

45. **Kamalova A. Yokutkhon, Sulaimonov Sh. Vakil**
FEATURES OF THE APPLICATION OF THERAPEUTIC PHYSICAL ACTIVITY IN
PATIENTS WITH CERVICAL OSTEOCHONDROSIS.....325

MORPHOLOGY

46. **Kuryazov K. Akbar, Olimov Sh. Siddik**
AGE-RELATED CHANGES IN ORTHOPEDIC STATUS IN WOMEN OF FERTILE
AGE.....331
47. **Khoshimov L. Bobur, Akhmedova M. Sayyora**
REACTIVE CHANGES IN THE AORTA IN EXPERIMENTAL METABOLIC
SYNDROME.....339
48. **Muzaffarova Sh. Nargiza, Sheryigitova I. Nigina, Azizov M. Mardon**
A NEW PERSPECTIVE ON THE ROLE OF VITAMIN D IN THE HUMAN BODY.....346
49. **Abdusattarov A. Adahamjon Alisherovich, Juraeva A. Mohigul, Ashuralieva A. Mavlyuda.**
THE CONCEPT OF FUNCTIONAL DYSPEPSIA.....353
50. **Oripov S. Firdavs Suratovich, Eshkabilova T. Surayo**
IMPACT OF ENERGY DRINKS COMPONENTS ON THE HUMAN BODY AND ITS
COMPLICATIONS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....361
51. **RADJABOV B. Akhtam**
MORPHOMETRIC CHARACTERISTICS OF INDICATORS OF PHYSICAL
DEVELOPMENT OF MALES IN POSTNATAL ONTOGENESIS AND IN CHRONIC
ALCOHOLISM.....368
52. **TILYABOV Ikram, USMANOV Ravshan**
MORPHOLOGICAL CHANGES OF THE KIDNEYS OF RATS IN DIABETES INDUCED
BY STREPTOZOTOCIN.....373

TRAUMATOLOGY AND ORTHOPEDICS

53. **Tilyakov B. Aziz, Tilyakov A. Xasan, Ayozbekov A. Zuhridin, Nabiyev A. Muhammadi**
CRITERIA FOR THE CHOICE OF TREATMENT AND DIAGNOSIS OF COMBINED
CHEST INJURIES IN PEDIATRIC PRACTICE.....383
54. **Tilyakov A. Xasan, Tilyakov B. Aziz, Temurov A. Alisher, Nomozov N. Fazliddin**
OPTIMAL METHODS OF CARE FOR VICTIMS WITH COMBINED BONE AND
VASCULAR INJURIES OF THE LOWER EXTREMITIES.....390
55. **Eranov N. Sherzod, Tilyakov A. Khasan**
ASSESSMENT OF X-RAY INDICATORS OF INSTABILITY OF THE DISTAL
RADIOULNARY JOINT IN CHILDREN.....401

56. **Fattakhov A. Ravshan, Nuritdinov A. Ulugbek**
 DISC DISLOCATIONS OF THE TEMPOROMANDIBULAR JOINTS (SCIENTIFIC REVIEW).....408

FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATION

57. **Iskandarov I. Alisher, Kaidarov A. Makhammadali**
 EXPERT ASSESSMENT OF THE INFORMATION CONTENT OF CLINICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS DURING THERMAL EXPOSURE ETHYLENE GLYCOL.....414
58. **Turonov Bobur Sobir ugli, Iskandarov Alisher Iskandarovitch**
 VISCERO-IRIDAL REFLEX CONNECTIONS IN THE MECHANISM OF IRIDOLOGY.....420
59. **Davranova E. Aziza, Toshmamatov Sh. Alimardon, Tashev Sh. Ulmas, Ganiev N. Sobirzhon, Kushbakov M. Akbar**
 FORENSIC CHEMICAL INVESTIGATIONS AND THEIR EFFECTIVENESS.....425

INFECTIOUS DISEASES

60. **Yarmuxamedova A. Nargiza, Yakubova S. Nigina, Mirzaeva U. Adolat**
 CLINICAL AND LABORATORY CHARACTERISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH TICK-BORNE RICKETSIOSIS IN THE SAMARKAND REGION.....434
61. **Achilova M. Matlyuba, Shodiyeva A. Dilafruz**
 ASSESSMENT OF THE SAFETY OF HIGHLY ACTIVE ANTIRETROVIRAL THERAPY IN PATIENTS WITH HIV INFECTION.....448
62. **Imamova A. Ilmira**
 RELEVANCE OF COVID-19 IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC VIRAL HEPATITIS.....453
63. **Allaberganova S. Zumrad, Karimova A. Maqsuda, Rajapov Y. Shahzod, Kurbanbaeva K. Dilnoza**
 STUDY OF THE CULTURAL AND PROTEOLYTIC PROPERTIES OF YEAST-LIKE FUNGI OF THE GENUS CANDIDA.....461
64. **Oslanov A. Absamat, Kodirov F. Jonibek, Samibaeva Kh. Umida, Suyarov A. Ulugbek, Qozieva L. Dilobar, Djumanazarov N. Sardorbek, Boysunov Ch. Shokhzod**
 SOME ASPECTS OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF MEASLES IN CHILDREN UNDER ONE YEAR OF ONE YEAR.....467

OPHTHALMOLOGY

65. **Yusupov F. Azamat, Khusanbaev Sh. Khasanjon, Abdullaeva I. Saida.**
 COMPLICATIONS OF DIABETIC RETINOPATHY AND THEIR SOLUTION.....475
66. **Xamidullayev F. Firdavs. Normatova M. Nargiza Nematulloev K. Tukhtasin**
 EFFECTIVENESS AND SAFETY OF BROLUCIZUMAB IN TREATING DIABETIC MACULAR EDEMA.....482
67. **Karimova Kh. Muyassar, Ubaydullaev O. Sardor**
 CLINICAL CASE OF IOL IMPLANTATION IN POSTVITRECTOMY EYE WITH APHAKIA.....491

ABASNIYA Surayyo Rasulovna

Urgench branch of Tashkent medical academy, Urgench, Uzbekistan

LABORATORY INDICATORS OF IMPROVING METHODS OF TREATING PERIODONTITIS AMONG THE POPULATION OF KHOREZM REGION

For citation: Abasniya R. Surayyo. Laboratory indicators of improving methods of treating periodontitis among the population of Khorezm region // Journal of Biomedicine and Practice. 2024, vol. 9, issue 2, pp. 182-186

 <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.11300549>

ABSTRACT

Laboratory parameters of saliva and oral fluid before and after treatment of chronic generalized periodontitis in patients in the Khorezm region were characterized. The characteristics of the place of residence of patients and their influence on the development of inflammatory periodontal diseases, the motivation of patients to treat periodontal diseases, the quality of dental care provided and the improvement of patient management taking into account statistical analysis were studied. The problems that arise in the diagnosis of inflammatory periodontal diseases and ways to solve them are discussed.

Keywords: saliva, oral fluid, chronic generalized periodontitis, laboratory parameters.

АБАСНИЯ Сурайё Расуловна

Ургенчский филиал Ташкентской медицинской академии

ЛАБОРАТОРНЫЕ ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЯ МЕТОДОВ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ПАРОДОНТИТА У НАСЕЛЕНИЯ ХОРЕЗМСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Охарактеризованы лабораторные показатели слюны и ротовой жидкости до и после лечения хронического генерализованного пародонтита у больных в Хорезмской области. Изучены особенности места проживания больных и их влияние на развитие воспалительных заболеваний пародонта, мотивацию больных к лечению болезней пародонта, качество оказываемой стоматологической помощи и усовершенствование ведения больных с учетом статистического анализа. Обсуждаются проблемы, возникающие при диагностике воспалительных заболеваний пародонта, и пути их решения.

Ключевые слова: слюна, ротовая жидкость, хронический генерализованный пародонтит, лабораторные показатели.

ABASNIYA Surayyo Rasulovna
Urgench branch of Tashkent medical academy, Urgench, Uzbekistan

XORAZM VILOYATI AHOLISIDA PARODONTITLARNI TAKOMILLASHGAN DAVOLASH USULLARINI LABORATORIYA KO'RSATMALARI.

ANNOTATSIYA

Xorazm viloyatidagi bemorlarda surunkali tarqoq parodontitni davolashdan oldin va davolashdan keyingi so'lak va og'iz suyuqligining laboratoriya ko'rsatkichlari tavsiflangan. Bemorlarning yashash joyining xususiyatlari va ularning yallig'lanishli parodontal kasalliklarning rivojlanishiga ta'siri, bemorlarni parodontal kasalliklarni davolashga motivatsiyasi, ko'rsatilayotgan stomatologik yordam sifati va statistik tahlilni hisobga olgan holda bemorlarni tekshirishni takomillashtirish o'rganildi. Yallig'lanishli parodontal kasalliklar diagnostikasida yuzaga keladigan muammolar va ularni hal qilish yo'llari ko'rib chiqiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: so'lak, og'iz suyuqligi, surunkali tarqoq parodontit, laboratoriya ko'rsatkichlari.

Relevance. The face plays an important role in the process of interpersonal communication and is the object of research of artists (artists, sculptors, artists), anatomists, psychologists, representatives of medicine: plastic surgeons, maxillofacial surgeons, dentists, dermatologists [Bratu D., Ieremia Z., Uram-Cuculescu S. (2003), A.P. Shurbeleva.(2003)]. In most cases, the therapeutic action is aimed at eliminating deformations, defects, and disproportions of the face, and the doctor should know and feel the individual harmony of the architectonics of each patient's face, the violation of which can have negative consequences – the loss of the individuality of the face. This may be the reason for a decrease in the attractiveness of the face to others. Namely, the desire to be attractive is inherent in most people, since an attractive face helps to establish interpersonal contacts, facilitates the solution of tender and career problems [Kovalenko A. V.(2011), Talalaeva E.V.(2012), Almstrand A.C., Josefson M., Bredberg A.(2010), A.P. Shurbeleva.(2003)]. The face largely determines its attractiveness and is the main means of identification and non-verbal communication. According to the results of a study by J. Garwill (1992), 63% of patients believe that their problems with appearance negatively affected their personal life, and 44% – on social life [Kovalenko A.V. (2011), A.P. Shurbeleva.(2003)]. Very often, it is the desire to improve the aesthetics of teeth and face that is the main reason for contacting an orthodontist (KochelJ.Etal., 2010) [Talalaeva E.V. (2012)]. The advertising of "anthropometric standards" by the mass media can be the cause of the formation of an inferiority complex in people with deviations in some parameters of the face architectonics and the cause of the emergence of a difficult-to-overcome need for reconstructive operations, which do not always bring them satisfaction, peace of mind and success in solving life problems [Baindurashvilia.A.(2011)]. Despite this, the authors' opinions on the prevalence and pathogenesis of this anomaly differ markedly. It is indicated that according to Bogatyrvkov D.V. et al. (2003), facial asymmetry occurs only in 1.3–2% of cases, whereas scientists at the University of North Carolina (1997) revealed clear signs of facial asymmetry in 34% of the examined patients, and Farkas L.G. and Chung G. (1981), using special anthropometric methods, found asymmetry in all the examined individuals. According to E.Y. Nikolaeva, such a difference in data can be explained, for example, by a wide variety of types of facial asymmetries: skeletal, functional, muscular, articular, as a result of neoplasms or inflammatory processes, as well as post-traumatic asymmetries resulting from improper fusion of the jaws after fractures. There is still no consensus on the question of whether E.Y. Nikolaeva (2009) comes to the conclusion of what is considered an asymmetry.

The purpose of this study. The aim is to improve methods for measuring morphometric features and diagnosing morphofunctional disorders of the maxillary system in people with chronic pathologies of the respiratory system.

Research objectives: 1. To identify age-related features of the growth of the gnathic part and the entire facial part of the skull and their effect on the sagittal and vertical dimensions of the face in normal and chronic pathologies of the respiratory system. 2. The tone of the masticatory muscles and

the circular muscles of the mouth were studied, its effect on the parameters of the facial skull in patients with chronic pathologies of the respiratory system will be determined. 3. To study the structural features of the facial part of the head in normal and chronic pathology of the respiratory system. 4. To study the clinical and statistical relationship between various telorentgenological parameters to improve the differential diagnosis of the maxillary system in normal and chronic pathology of the respiratory system. 5. To improve the clinical differential diagnosis of varieties of morphometric structures of the maxillary system in normal and pathological chronic respiratory failure. 6. To develop an algorithm for the diagnosis, treatment and prediction of deformation of the dental system in normal and chronic pathology of the respiratory system.

The material and the methods of research used to perform this research work. The research was conducted in Khorezm region. The facial skeleton and dental system of 300 healthy people and 300 people with chronic pathologies of respiratory systems aged from 18 to 60 years will be examined. The main criteria for the selection of people in the study group will be confirmed by morphometric, rengenological, orthopedic methods and clinical and laboratory studies. It should be noted that the examined will also be divided into age groups: by age 18-24 years, 25-34 years, 35-44 years and 45-60 years old and by severity of chronic respiratory pathology. The research program at all stages will include both traditional and special methods of clinical and dental examination. a) clinical and dental research methods b) study of functional occlusion and evaluation of conflict relationships c) anthropometric methods d) biometric study of diagnostic models of jaws e) study of facial proportions f) assessment of the degree of need for orthodontic treatment g) Enzyme immunoassay methods: immunoglobulin A, M, J, secretory immunoglobulin A, hormones (cortisol, TSH), antiproteases (ceruloplasmin, transferrin, antitrypsin, TNF- α , IL-1, 4, 6, 10, CRP). h) Biochemical methods: acid-base state of blood and saliva, lysosomal enzymes of blood and saliva, magnesium level in saliva); i) Functional methods: ultrasound, densitometric, X-ray, rheographic; j) statistical methods. For a long time, parodont diseases were considered as a process of focal infection with rare systemic consequences. However, in recent times, there have been more and more studies dedicated to the effects of parodont diseases on the common disease, and there are suggestions that this dependence can be in different directions. Over the past 20 years, doctors and scientists have been trying to explain correlation dependence between parodontitis and cardiovascular disease, diabetes, metabolic disorders and other diseases [2.4.6.8.10].

The risk of the occurrence of any disease is dynamic and will depend on the result of complex relationships of various factors that occur throughout life. Many variable risk factors, such as smoking and excessive calorie intake, lead to increased systemic markers of inflammation and can alter gene control through various biological mechanisms. This leads to a decrease in the body's response to various influences and adaptation norms. Parodontitis and other common chronic inflammatory diseases have several influencing risk factors such as tobacco smoking, psychological stress and depression, alcohol consumption, obesity, diabetes, metabolic syndrome and osteoporosis. In a series of studies, it has been shown that bacterial products, toxins and inflammatory products can spread to other foci of inflammation in the body when hygiene processes are carried out as a result of mechanical disruption of the integrity of the bioplionka [1.3.5.7.9.10]. In individuals with the right level of immune reaction, such transient bacteremia may not cause much harm. However, the immune system is weakened, such as diabetes, with diseases of the upper respiratory tract, making sufferers more prone. Considering chronic generalized parodontitis as a dysbiotic inflammatory disease with a negative impact on Systemic Health, one can speak of the appearance of dysbiotic processes in the oral cavity and their persistence, which indirectly develops an inflammatory reaction in the body [2,3]. In the literature, information about the increased dependence and susceptibility of chronic generalized parodontitis to cardiovascular diseases, diabetes, chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases (ocular) and other systemic diseases is increasingly found. Most of the incidence of cardiovascular diseases in parodontitis is based on the "general hypothesis of susceptibility". According to him, direct bacterial invasion of blood vessels or a systemic inflammatory reaction leads to an increase in circulating cytokines, which damage the vascular endothelium. Atherosclerosis, which was previously generally considered a lipid disorder, is currently an inflammatory disease. At the same time can explain the

causal relationship between parodontitis and atherosclerosis, for example, in the parodontal complex, the inflammatory-destructive process forms the translocation of bacteria to systemic blood flow, that is, it calls bacteriemia, which is confirmed in patients with parodontitis and can provide atherogenic stimulation. Systemic inflammation leads to an increase in the level of circulating cytokines, which are of interest, and includes S-reactive protein (SRO), interleukin-1 (il-1), interleukin-6 (il-6), α -tumor necrosis factor (Ono- α) and prostaglandin E2. Studies conducted, on the other hand, have shown that the stagnation of the inflammatory-destructive process in parodont affects the decrease in the acceleration of atherosclerosis of the carotid artery in humans [7.8.]. Many works are devoted to the connection of chronic parodontitis with such a metabolic disorder as diabetes mellitus. Today, when diabetes is considered as an additional symptom in nosology such as metabolic syndrome (MS), the information available helps to better understand the mechanism of pathogenesis. At the same time, their influence on each other is bilateral. Having diabetes in a patient leads to the fact that the hyperinflammatory response to the pathogenic microbiota of the parodont is reversible, worsens the return of inflammation and calls for a slowdown in recovery, which leads to a rapid violation of the parodont. Chronic generalized parodontitis, in turn, has a negative effect on glycemic levels in patients with diabetes mellitus and leads to the development of diabetic complications. The effect of parodontopatogens on the course of diabetes mellitus is explained by an increase in the level of systemic inflammatory mediators, which increases insulin resistance. Metaanalyses data allow us to talk about the fact that the treatment of generalized parodontitis in patients with diabetes mellitus leads to an improvement in glycemic index [8.9.10]. A number of authors in their work confirms the thesis that there is a bilateral relationship between diabetes and parodontitis, in which diabetes increases the risk of parodontitis occurring, while inflammation of the parodont negatively affects the glycemic index. Terminal stage cases of macroalbuminuria and renal insufficiency increase 2 and 3 times, respectively, in diabetics with severe parodontitis compared to diabetics without severe parodontitis. In addition, the risk of cardiorenal death (ischemic heart disease and diabetic nephropathy) in diabetics with severe parodontitis is 3 times higher than in diabetics without severe parodontitis. Treatment of parodontitis is associated with a reduction in glycosylated hemoglobin HbA(1C) by 0.4%.

At the same time, the authors came to the **conclusion** that the health of the oral cavity and the treatment of parodont are an integral part of the treatment of diabetes.

REFERENCES | ЧОҶКИ | IQTIBOSLAR:

1. Khabibova N.N. Characteristic features of free-radical processes and antioxidant protection in the oral cavity during chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis. *European Science Review*, 2018. - P. 191-193.
2. Khabibova N.N. Changes in biochemical and immunological indicators mixed saliva of patients with chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis. *European journal of pharmaceutical and medical research*, 2018; (5) 11: 143-145.
3. Khabibova N.N. Clinical and biochemical features of the course of pseudoallergic variants of chronic recurrent aphthous stomatitis. *Problems of biology and medicine*. – 2018; № 4 (104): 220-222. (in Russ).
4. Khabibova N.N., Saidov A.A., Saidov M.R. Peculiarities of lipid peroxidation and the state of oral antioxidant defense in chronic relapsing aphthous stomatitis. *A new day in medicine*, 2018, № 3 (23): 61-63. (in Uzb).
5. Qurbonova, N., Khabibova, N., & Ikhtiyarova, G. A. Hygienic condition of the oral cavity and the level of hygienic knowledge of silk motor workers. *European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine*, 2020; 7(3): 3027-3033.
6. Khabibova, N., Vakhidova, M. A., & Zhabborova, F. U. The effectiveness of complex therapy for generalized periodontitis in obese patients. *Eruditio Juvenium*, 2016; (2): 114-123. (in Russ)

7. Khabibova, N. Clinical and paraclinical parameters of blood and saliva in patients with periodontitis burdened with obesity. Doctor-graduate student, 2010;43(6.4): 510-514. (in Russ)
8. Turaeva F.A. Effectiveness of using modern methods and tools in periodontal inflammatory diseases. A new day in medicine. - Bukhara, 2020;2 (30):563-566. (in Uzb)
9. Turaeva F.A. Improving the Effectiveness of Treatment of Generalized Periodontitis Using Auto Platelet Mass. American Journal of Medicine and Medical Sciences - USA, 2020; 10 (8). N1: 576-579
10. Qurbonov D.F., Xabibova N.N., Eronov YO.Q. Prevention of dental diseases of the system pregnant women-women in labor-lactating women. NeuroQuantology, June 2022; 20(19): 18-29.

Статья поступила в редакцию 03.03.2024; одобрена после рецензирования 20.04.2024; принята к публикации 26.04.2024.

The article was submitted 03.03.2024; approved after reviewing 20.04.2024; accepted for publication 26.04.2024.

Информация об авторах:

Абасния Сурайё Расуловна – ассистент кафедры стоматологии Ургенчского филиала Ташкентской медицинской академии, Ургенч, Узбекистан. E-mail: suraya8089gmail@.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7115-4491>

Источники финансирования: Работа не имела специального финансирования.

Конфликт интересов: Авторы декларируют отсутствие явных и потенциальных конфликтов интересов, связанных с публикацией настоящей статьи.

Вклад авторов:

Абасния С.Р. — идеологическая концепция работы, редактирование статьи; сбор и анализ источников литературы, написание текста.

Information about the authors:

Surayyo R. Abasniya — assistant at the Department of Dentistry, Urgench branch of the Tashkent Medical Academy. Urgench, Uzbekistan; E-mail: suraya8089gmail@.com, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7115-4491>

Sources of funding: The work did not receive any specific funding.

Conflict of interest: The authors declare no explicit or potential conflicts of interest associated with the publication of this article.

Contribution of the authors:

Surayyo R. Abasniya — ideological concept of the work, editing the article; collection and analysis of literature sources, writing the text.

БИМЕДИЦИНА ВА АМАЛИЁТ ЖУРНАЛИ

9 ЖИЛД, 2 СОН

ЖУРНАЛ БИМЕДИЦИНЫ И ПРАКТИКИ

ТОМ 9, НОМЕР 2

JOURNAL OF BIOMEDICINE AND PRACTICE

VOLUME 9, ISSUE 2

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000